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Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

SOCIAL DIMENSION OF RURAL AREAS

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1. Summary and key messages

Previous studies have found that there is a low level of associative culture, weak social networks, lack of social venues, and low interest in public participation in rural areas in Aragón. At the same time, migrant population is becoming a challenge in rural areas as in some of the Aragón's counties they represent more than 25% of the population with a low inclusion level. This position paper focuses on the assessment of the needs related to social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas in Aragón as relevant components of the wellbeing in rural areas.

Drawing from literature review, surveys of the rural population, and discussions among MAP's members, the key messages of the IDRA position paper are that, although the quality of life in rural areas in Aragón is considered to be high by survey participants, many aspects related to the social dimension of rural development still deserve additional attention. Social relationships and social inclusion are among the most important aspects that contribute to the quality of life, but there is a need to strengthen social commitment through collective actions, enhance social integration of different generations and support work/free time conciliation, support capacity building of social agents and guarantee the social inclusion of migrant population.

To address these needs, additional limitations need to be overcome in parallel such as access to affordable housing, transport and mobility improvements, and increased availability of qualified jobs. In addition, in order to strengthen the social conditions of rural Aragón, it would be beneficial to ensure that the legislation developed is adapted to rural areas conditions (rural proofing), that appropriate control procedures are put in place, and that the coordination among the administrative bodies concerned increases.

Over the past decade, the Local Action Groups (LAGs) have become the principal social actors with the highest potential to overcome the social needs in rural areas in Aragón, as they count on a strong, participative social basis. However, LAGs do not have neither the structure nor the capacitation and funds to address social issues in a proper way, without additional support and coordination by responsible authorities.

The policy recommendations from the members of the MAP focus on two main areas:

1. Clearly define in social legislation the objectives, actions, and budgets dedicated to the diversity in rural areas (rural areas positive discrimination), accompanied by instruments for the evaluation of the impact of social policies. The legislative adaptation to rural areas and territorial approach also refers to other national regulations such as entrepreneurship and EU funds such as the European Social Fund.
2. Improve the role of the LAGs as main instrument to deal with the needs related to social relationships and inclusion. To this end, MAP's members provide several recommendations such as: i) to define the social objective for Leader at EU level more clearly; ii) to improve the multi-fund solution; iii) to promote results-oriented programs; and iv) to increase the support for projects aiming at intangible assets.

MAP's members identified the following research opportunities: 1) mechanisms on how to adapt social legislation to the needs of rural areas; 2) double direction knowledge transfer methods; 3) qualitative and quantitative dynamic models flexible enough to understand the functioning and relationships in the diverse rural areas; 4) understanding the decision-making of the actors in the rural areas and 5) methods for the evaluation of impact of social policies in rural areas; 6) evaluation of organisation of social politics in rural areas in Spain and 7) overcoming the significant data gaps at local level.

2. Introduction

This position paper is based in the definition of the social dimension provided in the SHERPA discussion paper, in which it is described as the relationships between people, i.e. social relationships. In SHERPA's project, it specifically refers to the relationships between people living in rural areas, which vary in intensity, extent, and quality, and which influence the life of the individual for better or for worse. As social dimension in rural areas encompasses a broad range of dimensions, four sub-topics were identified in the discussion paper: 1) wellbeing and social relationships in rural areas; 2) public goods provisioning and social networks; 3) bridging the rural-urban gap by promoting cultural activities; and 4) social inclusion of migrant population in rural areas.

Two sub-topics have been covered in this MAP position paper, the wellbeing and social relationships in rural areas and social inclusion of migrant population in rural areas. Wellbeing, mainly a subjective concept (ESS, 2013), is usually analysed by measuring the quality of life. There are many different initiatives attempting to measure the quality of life. For example, Eurostat (2021) has designed a multidimensional approach to measure quality of life that embraces eight dimensions, among which social interactions, such as activities with people, activities for people and supportive relationships are addressed. Eurofound (2022) adds new social dimensions when measuring the quality of life, such as trust and social tensions, social exclusion and support, and participation in society and community. The position paper places social relationships and social inclusion as key enablers of the quality of life in rural areas in Aragón.

Recent studies on life quality show that Aragón was the third Autonomous Community in Spain with the highest quality of life in 2019. Material conditions, jobs, education, leisure and social relationships, security and natural environment are the aspects that are above national average. In relation to social relationships, in 2019, the 94.5% of the Aragonese population has high or very high satisfaction with their personal relationships, 93.3% has relatives, friends or neighbours to ask for help in case of need, 97.8% has someone to talk to about personal issues and 58 percent has high or very high trust in others (Giménez Estaban, 2021).

The SWOT analyses conducted by the Local Action Groups (LAGs) in Aragón when defining their strategic plans 2014-2020 are rich sources of information to know the main weaknesses identified in the rural areas in Aragón regarding social relationships and inclusion. For example, many of the LAGs (ASOMO, 2017; ADIBAMA, 2017; ADRI-Jiloca, 2017; OMEZYMA, 2017; OFYCUMI, 2017; ASIADER, 2017) identified as weaknesses in their regions the low level of associative culture, the weak social networks, the lack of social venues, the low public participation interest of the rural inhabitants and the low cooperation level between civil associations and public administrations and across counties to face jointly the challenges. Additionally, vulnerable collectives such as the elder and youth people, women, disabled population, and migrants, also received special attention in the strategic plans. Migrant population is becoming a challenge in some of the Aragón's counties (ADRI-Jiloca, 2017; ADRAE, 2017; OFYCUMI, 2017; FEDIVALCA, 2017; CEDERZO, 2017; CEDER-Somontano, 2017; CEDEMAR, 2017; ADEFO, 2017) because their unemployment rate is high and their families are numerous and are under an increasing poverty risk. The migrants' language, culture, religion and their lack of knowledge about the local culture and customs as well as the low inclusive responses from the local population are some of the factors that explain the low inclusion rates of migrant population in rural areas in Aragón. Finally, the lack of initiatives that allow to conciliate labour and work hinders women and elder people inclusion in rural areas (ASOMO, 2017; CEDERZO, 2017; CEDER-Monegros, 2017; ADECUERA, 2017).

The aim of the position is to answer the following questions:

- What are the needs of rural areas in Aragón in relation to quality of life, social relationships and social inclusion?

- What are the policy interventions already in place, and what are examples of actions taken by local actors addressing these needs in Aragón?
- Which policy interventions (i.e. instruments, measures) are recommended by MAP members to be implemented at the local, regional, and/or national level? How can the EU support these interventions?
- What are the knowledge gaps and what research projects are needed?

3. Current situation based on background research and evidence

To address the quality of life, social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas two main actions have been conducted – desk research and the undertaking of a survey.

Firstly, desk research was conducted (see the detailed explanation in the Annex 1), through which the **quality of life** was assessed considering the time to access to basic services (Fernández and Santos, 2022) in the different Aragón’s counties classified according to the OCDE methodology (Brezzi, M., L. Dijkstra and V. Ruiz, 2011). According to the Figure 1, the time to access to basic services differs across county’s classification. While the time to access to the basic services is lower than 20 min in urban areas, it is higher than 20 minutes in “rural areas close to an urban center” and “rural remote areas”. Deeping on the services, the time to access to education and provisioning is lower than 20 minutes in every county’s classification; the time to access to health services is lower than 20 minutes in the urban areas, intermediate areas close to an urban areas, and intermediate remote areas. Finally, it takes more than 20 minutes to access to the respite care services in every county classification, except in urban areas. This may be explained by the fact that, as no data on the time to access to respite care activities is available, the time to access to the provincial capital has been selected as a proxy in this assessment

Figure 1. Time to access to basic services by type of county in Aragón

Source: Own elaboration based on Gobierno de Aragón (2021)

Regarding **migrant population** in rural areas in Aragón, migrants in Aragón has increased in the last years. While it was 6% of the total population in 2003 and it has increased up to 162.350 people in 2021 (INE, 2021), representing 12% of the total population, a higher rate than that of national average (10.69%). One fifth of the migrants come from the European Union (EU) and more than half of these EU immigrants come from Romania. More than one fifth of the immigrants come from Africa and more than half of these African immigrants come from Morocco. Two fifth of the immigrants come from Latin America and the last fifth is composed of migrants from non-EU countries, North America, Oceania and Asia (INE, 2021). Most of the migrant population get temporal jobs in services (47%) and agriculture (32%). According to CCOO (2020), the high level of temporality limits the access of migrant population to social protection and increases their social exclusion vulnerability. At county level, there are some counties where the increase of migrant population has been even more pronounced than at regional level. For example, migrant population in the county Bajo Aragón-Caspe has increased from 4% in 2003 to 25% in 2021 as an increasing number of temporary agricultural workers have decided to rest and root in the village (IAEST, 2021).

Besides desk research, a survey was conducted by the authors in June 2022 to gather information on rural population’s perception about their quality of life and social relationships (Annex 2). The 112 respondents are from 24 different Aragonese counties, most of them classified under predominantly rural remote areas (62%) and intermediate remote areas (25%). 53% women and 47% men, with an average age of 49 years dedicated to different economic/non-economic activities: service sector (29%), public sector (22%), retirees (18%), agricultural sector (1%), and other sectors (22%).

The result of the survey shows that the quality of life is perceived as high, 7.96 on a range from 1 to 10. Respondents were also asked to indicate which of the currently existing conditions that most contribute to their quality of life, see Figure 2 below. The environmental conditions is considered the conditions that most contribute to the quality of life followed by social conditions. On the other hand, access to employment and services was indicated as the condition that currently the least contributes to rural population’s quality of life.

Figure 2. Conditions that contribute to the quality of life in rural areas, scale from 0-7

Source: own elaboration based on the survey

The respondents were also asked to select the seven conditions that were considered most important to be improved in order to enhance the quality of life in rural areas (Figure 3). Interestingly, access to employment and services – above indicated as the category that least contribute to the quality of life – was by respondents perceived as the category that needs the greatest improvement in order to enhance the quality of life in rural areas. This result reflects that rural population prioritise the environmental and social conditions in their decision making in living in rural areas, even if the level of services is low.

Figure 3. Conditions that should be most improved to enhance the quality of life

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Additional questions were included in the survey to define the relationships in rural areas. According to the responses, the key results are the following:

- The aspects that most impede the existence of social relations are: the limited number of inhabitants, lack of interest, and mistrust in the results of collective action (Annex 3).
- Restaurants or nightlife venues are the places where the social relations are most easily established (Annex 4).
- Collaboration to organise leisure or cultural activities is easier than to provide mutual help or assistance in work activities or to organise new forms of service provision (Annex 5).
- Social relations do not always involve the whole population and different sub-groups stand out. For example, women have a more active social role than men and new population (national /international) is the least involved in social relationships (Annex 6 and 7).

4. Position of the Multi-Actor Platform

4.1. Identified needs

During a meeting in June 2022, members of the MAP IDRA identified the following needs related to the social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas. The identified needs are presented into two groups: Needs directly and indirectly related to social relationships. The needs directly related to social relationships are:

1- Reinforce social commitment with collective actions

MAP members highlighted the decreasing commitment to collective actions, including the lack of funds for investments in intangible assets as an urgent need to address in order to improve quality of life in rural areas in Aragón.

MAP members highlighted that nowadays there is a continuous loss of commitment with promoting collective actions. Just few people are interested in triggering collective activities, so those who still lead collective actions are involved in many different projects and they finally burn out. Therefore, collective actions are disappearing and being replaced by subcontracted actions. Indeed, traditional costumes that reinforce social relationships and promote collective actions are disappearing. For example, the custom called "Salir a la fresca" (going outside to enjoy the fresh evening breeze) in which the neighbours sat down in the street in the evening to talk and share their experiences and projects every day is a custom that is disappearing.

One clear example of the lack of interest of pursuing collective efforts is the increased challenge to find village mayors. Currently, this role is based on voluntary work and the mayors have to conciliate their remunerated work and personal lives with their commitment with the village's citizens. This opened the discussion among the MAP's members about the actions towards professionalise the villages' mayor by remunerating their work. There was no clear consensus between the MAP's members about whether this was a preferred option. On the one side, hiring the mayor could contribute to attract skilled people in rural areas capable to do it properly, and allow them to have work family balance as well as having time to improve the quality of life in villages. Those villages with a very low number of inhabitants, require mayors to devote an great amount of time to promote activities that to change the dynamics and avoid people keep moving out. On the other hand, MAP's members explained that hiring mayors is against the rural development philosophy and commitment. Mayors should be really committed to the village, with no additional incentive. In any case, MAP's members highlighted that the wellbeing in the villages much rely on the mayor.

The loss of collective actions is also explained by the increasing difficulty to fund intangible actions, as there are no clear indicators to check the investments and track the impacts. Hence, most of the funds are targeted to tangible project (i.e. fixed assets investments), lowering the interest to build up collective projects. The decreasing support to intangible projects has negatively impact the social dynamism.

The LAGs are carrying out a relevant role in rural areas, dynamising activities that reinforce social relationships. They are the link between the regional administration and the beneficiaries; they are close to the rural population and everyone who wants to build up a project or need any information, comes to the LAG. Furthermore, the LAG funds intangible projects through the budget line "cooperation projects", through which the LAGs of different counties collaborate to promote social networks. Some example of these cooperation projects are "Tribu rural"¹ to provide services to rural population (school transportation, school canteen, or English classes for adults and children), "Jóvenes dinamizadores" (dynamising youngsters)² to

¹<https://arainfo.org/tribu-rural-el-proyecto-de-cooperacion-entre-municipios-del-jiloca-para-propiciar-servicios-a-las-personas-que-viven-en-ellos/>

²<https://dinamizomipueblo.es/jovenes-dinamizadores-rurales-2/>

promote shared learning and seek common solutions to the specific needs of young people living in rural areas and "Concilia"³ to enhance rural women inclusion.

Finally, floating population was also identified as a key group to carry out community work. When they come back to rural areas in holidays or weekends, this population is a driver to keep traditional festivals and activities. It would be advisable to find the way to make the most of this population and help prolong their presence in rural areas.

2.- Social integration of different generations and life conciliation

Members of the IDRA MAP believe that the low number of people living in rural areas leads to the need of defining social relationships from a new perspective. While relationships between different age-groups are also weak in rural areas improving them is necessary to promote revitalisation activities in which all the age-groups participates coordinated and age-group relationships turn strengthened. Each age-group has its own values, such as the energy of the younger and the resources and experience of the elderly. The real challenge is how to coordinate these interactions.

For example, this kind of coordination could be applied to support the mayor's office. A young mayor of the village with energy and innovative ideas, but with not enough time to dedicate to the mayor's office as he /she has to attend other labour and family duties, can be supported by retired workers, with available time, experience, and networks.

In this regard, there is a need to promote activities oriented to the family as a whole, including children and elders to facilitate the participation in collective actions. Indeed, this integral approach would benefit the most vulnerable groups (migrant population) with no funds to leave children with anyone else to take care of them to be able to participate in the collective actions. Schools and educative community are important actors to promote family activities.

3.- Support dynamisation capacities of the social agents in rural areas

There is no positive discrimination for rural citizens to get jobs at local (county) public entities, for example as social agents/technicians. MAP's members agreed that technical experts from rural areas are more committed and can revitalise rural areas to a greater extent than those technicians who live in urban areas. They know the rural needs based on their own experience, live close to the rural population and can attend most of the rural invigoration activities, even if they take place during the weekend. On the opposite side, technicians from urban areas come back home once the working day is finished. As there are such a few technicians working in rural areas, if some of them do not dynamise properly the impact of his/her incomplete work is more evident.

4.- Social inclusion of migrant population

There is an important need of improving migrant population inclusion, and rural population is key to promote actions that facilitate their inclusion. The presence of migrant population is increasing in rural areas in Aragón. In many villages, the 30% of the children belong to migrant families. Indeed, there are villages where the migrant children represent the 50% of the children. For example, in one village there are 22 children. 11 out of 22 of them are migrant children and 6 out of 11 are Moroccan. This situation is mainly explained by two factors: i) the low number of children in rural areas; and ii) the size of the migrant families; while Spanish families have one or two children per family, migrant families, mainly Moroccan families, have four/five children per family.

³ <https://concilia.org/>

MAP members explained that while there are no differences when children are younger than 6 years, differences arise when children start primary education as they commonly do not attend birthday parties, neighbours' meetings or other social activities. Thus, the inclusion of migrant children outside of school is limited. This situation mainly happens with Moroccan migrants and not with other nationalities such as Romanian, Ukrainian and Latin American migrants with whom there are few inclusion problems. Moroccan families are in general poor and have to sustain many children. In some cases, they do not have legal residence, so they have just access to jobs with low work conditions. Therefore, they do not have the resources to maintain the way of living of the rest of the neighbours, to go out and to participate in leisure activities.

Social inclusion is even more complicated with roman families, as the neighbourhood directly relates this ethnicity with problems and lack of security.

The MAP's members as key actors to reinforce the inclusion of migrant population identify the educative community (school and parents' associations). There is a common perception that migrant population (mainly Moroccan) do not want to be included but it is important to move beyond this perception. There are many things to do, and more commitment of the educative community is needed. It has been already tested that for example sports are relevant drivers to promote social inclusion of the children and their families, as well as organising activities such as celebrating the "country days" to show the relevance of the cohabitation of different countries.

Finally, it was also identified by the MAP's members that there are just a few public services in the rural areas targeted to reinforce social inclusion of migrant population. Though the public administration of the county hires social workers, they are not enough and they do not pay much attention to this collective. Migrant population is mainly supported in rural areas by Non-Governmental Institutions, such as Red Cross, and just in those areas where they are present.

Regarding national new entrants, MAP's members argued that the number of people living in the villages is so low the impact of new entrants is evident and relevant. New entrants are usually questioned by residents. There is a general mistrust in the activities they will be conducting and the time they will be able to keep them and living in the rural area. As clearer are the way of living of the new entrants easier is their inclusion.

In addition, the MAPs members identified the following **needs related to the other quality of life dimensions** that in turn relates to social dimensions (indirectly related):

1. Quality of life in rural areas – it is not a matter of lack of access to services

As explained in previous section, the survey shows that people in rural areas perceived they have a high quality of life. MAP members explained these positive results arguing that people live in rural areas because they want; rural life is the way of living that rural population has selected. Those who did not like rural areas have already gone. In this sense, the perceived quality of life of women is very important; particularly in those families in which just the husband/partner has a job. In those cases, if women wants to live in the rural area the whole family will remain, even if men must travel every day from the village to the city to work.

Rural areas do not have serious challenges related to access to services such as education or health. Though these services could be improved in particular in small villages, their current state do not limit the quality of life of rural population. Furthermore, according to MAP's members, the access to services has already reached a level that improving it will neither attract more people nor drive out rural population. Those who decided to move to urban areas will not come back because of increased services access. It is difficult to get this population back as they decided to move for different reasons. Furthermore, when services access is addressed, it is important to consider that the time to access services is not the unique variable, but also the quality of the services and variety of the services. The quality of some health services is better in rural areas

than in urban areas. For example, the waiting lists in hospital and specialists may be shorter in county capitals compared to the regional capitals.

2.- Access to housing

There is a real need to improve the access to housing. It is necessary to change the rental market dynamics. Most of the owners of rural properties prefer not to rent, as they have no trust in rent legislation/market. Furthermore the quality of housing is bad (lack of heating/ proper insulation, leak and moisture) and prices are high. The alternative is to rehabilitate the damage houses or build new ones. The conditions to access the aids to doing so are so complex that potential beneficiaries refuse to get them and move to the cities.

An idea proposed by the MAP's members is to rehabilitate the big houses in which live one/two people and divide them into small apartments for rent.

3.- Transport and mobility

MAP's members highlighted that improving transports and mobility between villages is very important. There are still some private initiatives that cover this need but they are not coordinated and standardised.

4.- Availability of qualified jobs

One of the challenges faced by rural population is the lack of qualified works. New private initiatives could be a source of new qualified jobs but, as explained before, most of them failed as normative and aids do not fit the entrepreneurs' needs.

In addition, instruments to support job creation do not fit rural needs. For example, many of the current instruments encourages "green jobs", but rural workers require aids to set up professions such as plumber, carpenter, bakers who have no direct relationship with these categories and hence are not supported.

There is a need to improve the rural job pools. Though some the LAGs support the rural job pools (Rural Jobs: <https://pueblosvivosaragon.com/rural-job/>), this service is not extended to the whole territory. The Autonomous community also provides information about available jobs (Employment Institute of Aragón-INAEM: <https://inaem.aragon.es/>) but potential employees have to be subscribed to receive jobs information, and rural employers do not have the option to filter potential employees living in rural areas, in case the prioritise rural employees to hire.

5.- Develop rural proofing. Legislation should be adapted to rural areas conditions

One of the main barriers to revitalise rural areas is the lack of adaptation of the different legislations to rural specifics, mainly related to the size of the projects (level of investment or number of beneficiaries) or the nature of the activity. For example, the regulation and conditions to set-up nursery schools require great investments in housing conditions with no considerations the low number of children that will be attending. The direct impact is that those initiatives that can create new jobs do not take place.

MAP's members agreed that it is not a matter of more funds. There is a need of defining a legislation with a new rural view: There is a need to reinforce the rural proofing, examining government interventions closely from a rural perspective throughout their development and adjusting them as needed to ensure that their intended outcomes could be realised in rural areas. To this regard, the Spanish Government announced in January 2022 the future tabling of new legislation defining a new "Statute of the small municipalities (with population lower than 5.000 inhabitants)" adapting the existing municipal regulations on procedure, procurement and management to this new the local regime more adapted to the need of the rural municipalities. The government also proposed to update the Spanish Basic Municipal Law (Ley de Bases del Regimen local) implement digital procedures to reinforce public participation and digital vote of the councillors. One of the main results of these reforms will be to increase the presence of the local council in

rural development. Local councils will be able to manage the 15% of the national budget of the EU recovery plan.

Rural proofing depends not only on the legislator's intelligence but also, and with relevant role, on that of those who interpretate the normative and communicate to beneficiaries, i.e., public administrations at different regional levels. To this regard, the same normative has resulted in different impacts in diverse regions depending on the public administrations' interpretation. It can be explained by the fact that the relevant officials do not have enough information and education to correctly interpretate and applied the rules

There is also a need to improve public participation in the definition of the rural development strategies. These processes are characterised by the lack of a representative and unbiased participation. Not all the stakeholders (rural and urban population) take part in participatory processes. Furthermore, increasing transparency is required, as participation is limited to propose changes in a document already written; participating in the definition of the main in the definition of the rationale of the strategy is not encouraged. The quality of the strategy definition and its application need further improvement.

6. Limit the control procedures and improve coordination

There is a need to define subsidy controls and bureaucratic procedures with a new rural lens. The excessive requirements for being beneficiaries of subsidies do not consider the limitations of the rural population. The disproportionate the ex-ante procedures to the rural population' needs makes it for them difficult to apply, so that potential beneficiaries decide not even to apply, leaving important quantities of unspent funds.

Policy makers in the MAP explained that there is an emerging change towards the Anglo-Saxon model, in which the ex-ante control is replaced by an ex-post control. This way, the beneficiaries sign a responsibility statement to receive the grant. Once the project has been implemented, an ex-post auditory is conducted. This new procedure speeds up and facilitates the access to funds and will contribute to revitalise rural areas. But it requires a cultural/behavioural change in both sides of the process: the Administration should have a higher trust on beneficiaries' behaviour, and beneficiaries should have a higher commitment once the responsible statement is signed.

Furthermore, the MAP's members also highlighted that there is a need to better coordinate the advisory services provided by different administrations (Country administration, regional administrations, LAGs). Beneficiaries receive information from several sources that not always are aligned. Public Administration should be properly trained and timely informed. Furthermore, a personalised assistance could be designed, assigning one mentor to the beneficiaries who follows their trajectories in the long-term and avoid information conflicts.

Finally, there is a need to improve the services provided by the municipal administration. On one side, it is needed to strengthen the relationship between technicians working at the provincial administration (social workers, tourism and youths) and rural population. Incentives could be defined to strengthen their commitment with rural population. On the other side, the councillors should also increase their commitment with the rural areas and reinforce the long-term strategies in social inclusion, youth and tourism.

4.2. Existing interventions and actions

In Aragón, there are 20 LAGs⁴ (Annex 8) funded by the community-led European funding programme LEADER, which are the main actors promoting activities to reinforce **social relationships in rural areas**. The assessment of the strategic plans 2014-2020 of sixteen LAGs shows the LAGs' budgets vary from 2 million € (CEDEMAR) to almost 6 million € (CEDERZO) (Figure 4). In relative terms, the LAGs dispose

⁴ <https://aragonrural.org/grupos-leader/>

between 100-300 €/inhabitant for the period 2014-2020, except ASIADER which operates in a high depopulated region (5.013 inhabitants) resulting in a budget of 900€/inhabitant (Annex 9).

Figure 4. 2014-2020 Budget of Local Action Groups in Aragón

Source: Own elaboration based on the LAGs' 2014-2016 strategic plans (ADECUARA (2017); ADEFO (2017); ADIBAMA (2017); ADRAE (2017); ADRI-Jiloca (2017); ADRI-Teruel (2017); ASIADER (2017); ASOMO (2017); CEDEMAR (2017); CEDER-Monegros (2017); CEDER-Somontano (2017); CEDERZO (2017); CEDESOR (2017); FEDIVALCA (2017); OFYCUMI (2017); OMEZYMA (2017).

The analysis of the LAGs' budget allocations shows that funds are mainly allocated into projects to support business (agri-business, non-agribusiness and forestry) (Figure 5). Except some variations among LAGs, the budget allocated into ITC projects, environment conservation and cooperation projects are those with the lowest budget allocated in most of the LAGs. Based on the information provided by the MAP members, the main budget line that supports social relationships and inclusion is the budget line "Cooperation projects". As figure 5 shows the budget allocated on cooperation projects is lower than 10% in most of the LAGs, except in OFYCUMI (17%) and ASIADER and ADEFO.

Figure 5. LAGs' budget allocated by budget line

Source: Own elaboration based on the LAGs' 2014-2016 strategic plans (ADECUARA (2017); ADEFO (2017); ADIBAMA (2017); ADRAE (2017); ADRI-Jiloca (2017); ADRI-Teruel (2017); ASIADER (2017); ASOMO (2017); CEDEMAR (2017); CEDER-Monegros (2017); CEDER-Somontano (2017); CEDERZO (2017); CEDESOR (2017); FEDIVALCA (2017); OFYCUMI (2017); OMEZYMA (2017).

Some examples of the cooperation projects in which most of the LAGs in Aragón are involved are:

- “Pon Aragón en tu mesa”⁵: A project that values the quality of agri-food products produced in the rural environment of Aragón, helping to spread the word and communicating the quality of the Aragonese agricultural products. The project seeks to reinforce the agri-food entrepreneurship and short channels and boost consumption of Aragonese products.
- “Jovenes dinamizadores rurales”⁶: Several initiatives have been carried out under this project. Regarding social relationships, it is worthy to highlight the development of cooperative labs (https://dinamizomipueblo.es/portfolio_page/coworking-rural/) as spaces for socialisation, training, exchange of ideas, and strengthening of the community.
- “Calidad rural”⁷ a project that seeks to differentiate the quality of products made in rural areas under social responsibility parameters. ADIBAMA, ADRI Calatayud-Aranda, ADRI Jiloca-Gallocanta, BAJO ARAGÓN-MATARRAÑA, in collaboration with the County of Matarraña and CEDER Somontano are involved in this cooperation project.

In relation to **migrant inclusion**, the Spanish government approved in July 2022 the reform of the Immigration Law to facilitate the access to the labour market for foreigners in Spain, through the reduction of procedures and the creation of new channels to request employment permits. It is expected that it will impact on labour and social situation of migrant population in rural areas. At regional level, the Aragonese Government designed the Comprehensive Plan for the Management of Cultural Diversity in Aragon, 2018-2021⁸, though no specific mentions to migrant inclusion in rural areas are included in the plan. On April 2022, the regional government issued a tender to promote activities, conducted by NGOs, that facilitate inclusion of vulnerable communities ([ORDEN CDS/555/2022](https://orden.cds/555/2022)), such as personal (personal development family support, health support, training), cultural, residential and economic activities. As in the previous initiative, there is no specific mention to migrant inclusion in rural areas. The General Directorate of Cooperation for Development and Immigration, that belongs to the Department of Citizenship and Social Right of the Government of Aragón, launched in 2022 an awareness campaign on the rights of the temporary migrant workers⁹. Finally, the government of Aragón is participating until 2023 in the European project MATILDE¹⁰ aimed at promoting migrants’ inclusion in rural communities.

Additional inclusion-oriented services are coordinated by the Prevention and Social Inclusion Services that belongs to the General Social Services of the Aragonese Government. These services are provided at local level by the social services centres of municipalities. For example, the council of Valdejalón launched a campaign to promote the inclusion of temporary migrant workers¹¹.

Regarding the **actions taken by local actors**, information gathered from the surveys indicate that there is a wide variety of actions conducted by local actors that reinforce social relationships in rural areas across Aragón, such as organising sports events, cultural and gastronomic festivals, entertainment events, excursions, adult education classes. A selection of concrete actions related to the needs identified in the previous section is summarised in Table 1.

⁵ <https://ponaragonentumesa.com/>

⁶ <https://dinamizomipueblo.es/>

⁷ <https://calidadruralaragon.com/>

⁸ https://transparencia.aragon.es/sites/default/files/documents/2018_10_31_plan_gestion_diversidad_cultural.pdf

⁹ <https://www.aragon.es/documents/20127/89840701/CampDVPTT-Ingles.pdf/9a14134d-567d-3828-37dc-e208d77684c3?t=1620131893239>

¹⁰ <https://matilde-migration.eu/project-partners/government-of-aragon/>

¹¹ <http://www.valdejalon.es/programa-inmigrantes-y-temporeros>

Table 1 – Examples of actions taken by local actors

<p>Need: Housing</p> <p>Title: Co-housing La Vereda</p> <p>Text: The aim of the project is to build houses and common spaces led by group of people, following a cohousing model.</p> <p>Link: https://proyectolavereda.wordpress.com/</p>
<p>Need: Familial conciliation</p> <p>Title: Casas canguro (Kangaroo Houses)</p> <p>Text: Local conditioned to take care of children but that does not use the nursery or school regulations Childish. It is a special adaptation for areas uninhabited or with great dispersion of population.</p> <p>Link: http://www.pirineodigital.com/actualidad/abril03.htm</p>
<p>Need: Familial conciliation</p> <p>Title: School with hart</p> <p>Text: The school carry out many activities, in which fathers, mothers and grandparents collaborate in the development of the school garden and other activities of the center.</p> <p>Link: https://ganasdevivir.es/ceip-san-gregorio-de-ontinena-una-escuela-con-corazon-rural/</p>
<p>Need: Social inclusion</p> <p>Title: Nuevos senderos (New trials)</p> <p>Text: To promote the mobility of individuals and migrant families from urban areas to rural areas, turning them into a context of job opportunities and improvement of their quality of life. Migrant people are in turn agents of revitalisation and development of rural communities receiving</p> <p>Link: http://nuevossenderos.es/</p>
<p>Need: Social inclusion</p> <p>Title: Volver al pueblo (Coming back to the village)</p> <p>Text: To create the website Volveralpueblo.org aimed at new settlers and people at risk of exclusion, to offer a house bank (for lease or assignment) and job and business proposals in the areas most affected by the rural exodus.</p> <p>Link: http://volveralpueblo.org</p>
<p>Need: Social inclusion</p> <p>Title: Aventura multicultural en un pueblo aragonés (Multicultural adventure in a village in Aragón)</p> <p>Text: A coexistence plan to enhance cultural diversity.</p> <p>Link: https://www.caritas.es/blog/aventura-multicultural-pueblo-aragones/</p>
<p>Need: Reinforce social networks and collective actions</p> <p>Title: Proyecto arraigo (Roots project)</p>

Text: Platform dedicated to urban people interested in rooting in rural areas. This project arises from the disconnection between urban people who want to live in the rural environment and the rural population who want to receive population but do not get to it. The platform reinforces, trust, hospitality and coexistence.

Link: <https://proyectoarraigo.es>

Need: Reinforce social networks and collective actions

Title: La riada, Red Intermunicipal Aragonesa de Acción

Text: The aim is to organise participatory days in different locations to exchange information and projects with other people who also live in rural zones. The action is carried out by volunteers with common interests who observe the need to reinforce social networks.

Link: <https://twitter.com/redriada>

Need: Services provision

Title: Multiservicios Rurales (Rural multi-services)

Text: Start-up of business initiatives in municipalities where there are no activities basic such as a shop, bar and/or rural accommodation.

Link: <http://www.multiserviciorural.com>

Need: Movility and transport

Title: Ruralcar

Text: RuralCar is a non-profit collaborative economy initiative. This is a ride-sharing platform for rural environments to solve the lack of transports in rural areas and reinforce the connectiveness among villages. The design of the app is elder people oriented, considering that they are the most vulnerable collective.

Link: <https://ruralcar.org/>

4.3. Recommendations from the MAP

4.3.1. Recommendations for future rural policies

MAP members recommended the following policy interventions to be implemented to strengthen the social relationships, conciliation and inclusion in rural areas in Aragon at different regional levels:

MAP members proposed several recommendations to improve social policies at national and regional level:

- To **define a positive discrimination of rural areas** when defining **social policies at regional level**. The territorial dimension should be taken into account because rural areas are clearly context specific and diverse. Indeed, rural population is increasingly polarised (intensive vs extensive production, renewable energy vs tourism...). For example, as explain in the previous section, there is no mention to the specificities of the rural areas in the Comprehensive Plan for the Management of Cultural Diversity in Aragon, 2018-2021.

MAP's members propose the following alternatives to better adapt the regulations to rural realities: 1) define opt outs for rural areas in the existing legislation in those areas where it has been proven that rural areas are more vulnerable; 2) Reform of the Basic Statute of less population Municipalities guaranteeing equal opportunities to them. Additionally, further education and training to local

governments' staff would be needed to get the best interpretation and major impact of the existing legislation.

- To **define more/appropriate funds to social objectives at regional level**, to be able to rely less on the work of the LAGs. Most of the initiatives towards strengthening social relationships and inclusion are triggered by LAGs in Aragón, and with the current level of funding LAGs cannot be expected to take on all the objectives proposed rely just on them. To this end, it is proposed to **better coordinate the regional funds aimed at social objectives**.
- To pursue and develop **instruments for the evaluation of the impact of social policies** in rural areas.
- At national level, the Spanish government approved in March 2021 130 measures to deal with the demographic challenge (MITECO, 2021). These measures are classified under 10 axis. Though the identified social dimension needs are addressed in the axis 5 (equality in rights and opportunities in rural areas), the axis 8 (wellbeing and care economy), measures proposed are not feasible enough. MAP members recommend **defining concrete actions supported by allocated budgets and execution agenda**.

Regarding increasing social inclusion in rural areas, MAP members valued the positive impact of migrant families in rural areas arguing that they bring "life" to villages, labour force and contribute to keep social services operative. MAP members identified concrete recommendations to retain migrant population in rural areas such as: 1) **strengthen education/training/adult education** under a gender approach and in accordance with local labour needs; 2) **reinforce public transport services** (as they do not have private transport) and access to affordable housing; and 3) develop **activities that favour integration** such as sports and (bi-directional) intercultural activities. The leadership and responsibility of these actions should be clearly assigned to the corresponding authority and count on adequate budget.

Strengthening social networks, conciliation and inclusion requires to be close to the beneficiaries in the field, and flexibility to be able to respond in time. At local level, MAP members recommended that regional authorities should **increase confidence in the participation of civil society and LAGs in the definition of the social objectives and implementation of social actions**. This confidence could be expressed through a: 1) clear definition of the social commitments assumed by the LAGs, 2) adequate allocation of budget on social commitments; and 2) lower rigidity in the inter-governmental relationships.

This last point leads to the below recommendations on how to **strengthen the social dimension of Leader** in Aragón:

- At EU level, MAP members recommended to concretely **define the social objective for LEADER at EU level**. LEADER and the LAGs in Aragón have become the main instrument to support social relationships and social inclusion, so this aim should be more clearly defined among the Leader goals. Furthermore, MAP members discussed that a solution could be to move LEADER budget from the European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD) to cohesion funds. An additional way to increase the economic support to LAGs at EU level proposed by MAP members is to **improve multi-fund delivery**. Current conditions of the multi-fund approach do not create the adequate confidence environment for the actors to engage and the process is too bureaucratic and complicated. Finally, MAP members recommend defining territorial criteria in EU funds, such as the European Social Fund.
- At national/regional level, MAP members recommend reducing rigidity coming from the extremely detailed rules that limits the LAGs innovative actions and reinforcing the government trust in the LAGs. Furthermore, MAP members suggested to develop **results-oriented programmes** and **increase the support (financial and know-how and time-frame) for projects aiming at intangible assets**.

There was no clear consensus between policy and civil society (LAG) members of the MAP regarding the following policy recommendations:

- Referring to the LAGs strategic plans, some of the MAP members (mainly policy-focused members) proposed to **strengthen the added value of the strategic plans** and develop them towards strategic plans that captures all needs and strengths of a territory, i.e., a kind of territory strategic plan. To this regard, MAPs members representing civil society (LAGs) argued that with the current funding available for the activities of the LAGs, the purpose of this exercise is not clear and to do it properly the LAGs need additional resources – both time and funds. LAGs members proposed to reinforce the support to improve the **participative processes for the design of strategic plans** for the LAGs.
- The second recommendation that did not gather a clear agreement among MAP members was how to free up funds and time for LAGs to do less administrative burden, going back to their original social innovation purpose. Policy members of the MAP proposed to **create a new administrative figure that serves as umbrella for the LAGs** to conduct all the administrative processes. To this regard, MAP participants representing civil society were worried about losing autonomy and decision-making power.
- The third recommendation that was not agreed relates to how prioritise and create the maximum outcome from the limited funds of LEADER. Policy members from the MAP proposed the definition of a **large scale demonstration project** – one per LAG - to show leadership and inspire other projects to detect where there is potential for rural innovation. On the other hand, civil society (LAGs), preferred less money for more diverse projects, which will have greater intangible impacts. LAGs claimed that public administration prefers projects with tangible outputs over intangible ones, as their impact is easier to measure and monitor. By contrast, LAGs prioritised promoting intangible projects, where the need is the greatest.

4.3.2. Recommendations for future research agendas

MAP members identified the following knowledge gaps:

1. Research on mechanisms on how to **adapt social legislation to the needs of rural areas**.
2. Research on **double direction of knowledge transfer** methods. MAP members explained that there are already many studies in rural areas but they neither reflect their needs comprehensively nor provide applicable results.
3. Develop qualitative and quantitative **dynamic models** flexible enough to understand the functioning and relationships in the diversity of rural areas.
4. Research on **understanding the decision-making of the actors** in the rural areas.
5. Research effort to **overcome the significant data gaps at local level** for measuring impact of social policies – nor homogenous data, nor data over time.
6. Research on methods for the **evaluation of impact of social policies** in rural areas
7. On More research on the evaluation of governance differences among Spanish regions of **organisation of social politics**: Decision-making at different levels, drawbacks and duplicities implementing policy instruments.

Conclusions

This position paper analyses the needs around social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas in Aragón as relevant components of the wellbeing in rural areas. This document also reflects the research opportunities and policy recommendations suggested by MAP members to overcome the identified needs. To this end a combination of methods has been applied, comprising a review of the literature and ongoing initiatives, a survey and two workshops with MAP members.

Results from the literature review and survey reflects that quality of life in the rural areas in Aragón is high and that the social relationships and inclusion are some of the most important aspects for the population to perceive this high rate of quality of life. However, social relationships in rural areas are limited mainly explained by the limited number of inhabitants, low participation of new population (national /international), lack of interest, and mistrust in the results of collective action. Hence, actions are needed to improve social relationships and hence wellbeing.

Looking deeper into the needs of social relationships and inclusion in those areas, MAP members highlighted the need to reinforce social commitment with collective actions, to enhance social integration of different generations and life conciliation, to support capacity building of social agents in rural areas and to guarantee the social inclusion of migrant population. MAP members also identified additional needs indirectly related to social needs but also key to be overcome, such as improving housing access, transport and mobility, qualified jobs availability, develop legislation adapted to rural areas conditions (rural proofing), limit the control procedures, and improve administrative coordination.

The assessment of the existing interventions reflects results in line with the needs identified by MAPs members mainly in relation to the lack of adaptation of social legislation to the rural dimension and add additional needs related to the limited orientation of the LAGs budget to cover social needs. The latest LAG strategic plan shows that LAGs interventions have been mainly oriented to support the economic revitalisation rather than strengthening social relationships, despite the fact that they are key actors for that. Regarding migrant inclusion, they are no clear competences/budget among different regional authorities to address this issue in rural areas.

MAP members propose the following recommendations to improve social policies at national and regional level: 1) define a positive discrimination of rural areas when defining social policies at regional level; 2) define and/or appropriate funds to social objectives at regional and local level; 3) better coordinate the regional funds aimed at social objectives and improved coordination in social funds allocation in the territory; 4) develop instruments for the evaluation of the impact of social policies ; 5) increase confidence in the participation of civil society and LAGs in the definition of the social objectives and implementation of social actions. On the latter, MAP members propose the following recommendations to strengthen the social dimension of Leader in Aragón: i) define the social objective for Leader at EU level; ii) improve the multi-fund solution; iii) promote results-oriented programs; and iv) increase the support for projects aiming at intangible assets.

Finally, MAP members identified the following research opportunities: 1) mechanisms on how to adapt social legislation to the needs of rural areas; 2) double direction knowledge transfer methods; 3) qualitative and quantitative dynamic models flexible enough to understand the functioning and relationships in the diverse rural areas; 4) understanding the decision-making of the actors in the rural areas and 5) methods for the evaluation of impact of social policies in rural areas; 6) evaluation of the organisation of social policy and legislation in rural areas in Spain and 7) overcoming the significant data gaps at local level.

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Annex 1 Methodology used by the MAP

Responsibility: Facilitator and Monitor

Previous to organise the workshop with the MAP's members, desk research was conducted to gather information about the quality of life, social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas in Aragón. To this end, the counties in Aragón were classified (Figure a) according to their level of rurality following the OECD methodology (Brezzi, M., L. Dijkstra and V. Ruiz, 2011), that groups the counties into five categories of areas regarding the population living in an urban centre and the proximity to a city with a population of more than 50.000 inhabitants as follows:

- **Predominantly urban**, if 15% or less of its population live outside an urban centre.
- **Intermediate close to an urban centre**, if the population living outside an urban centre makes between 15% and 50% of its total population and if the time to access a provincial capital is less than 45 min.
- **Intermediate remote**, if the population living outside an urban centre makes between 15% and 50% of its total population and if the time to access a provincial capital is more than 45 min.
- **Predominantly rural close to an urban centre**, if 50% or more of its population live outside an urban centre and if the time to access a provincial capital is less than 45 min.
- **Predominantly rural remote**, if 50% or more of its population live outside an urban centre and if the time to access a provincial capital is more than 45 min.

Figure a. Classification of the counties in Aragón according with the rurality level.

Source: Own elaboration based on Gobierno de Aragón (2021)

Based on Fernández and Santos, 2022, the quality of life in counties has been assessed by measuring the time to access five major basic conditions: work, education (primary and secondary schools), care (pharmacy, hospital, specialty care centre, health centre, emergency centre and primary care attention centre), provisioning (supermarket) and rest (time to access to leisure, sports and cultural activities). Fernández and Santos, 2022 introduce the concept of the “20-20 limit” which means that when the service to fulfil a basic need is lower than 20 min by car or more than 20 km away the quality of life of the inhabitants is good.

A survey was designed and conducted to gather information about the perceived quality of life of people living in rural areas in Aragón, as well as social relationships and social inclusion. The survey considers the dimensions identified in previous initiatives (Eurostat, 2021; Eurofund, 2022) and is detailed in Annex 2.

Once the survey’s results were analysed, the first workshop with the MAP’s members were organised. It was held the 28th of June in Zaragoza (Aragón), it lasted four hours and it was structured as follows:

- 1) Introduction: Definition of the social dimension and its relationship with the quality of life in rural areas
- 2) The case of Aragón: Approaches to the measurement of quality of life in rural areas.

- 3) Diagnosis of the social dimension of the rural areas of Aragon. Presentation of results of surveys of the rural population in Aragon:
 - a) Perception of quality of life. Discussion
 - b) Needs identification: Which are the most relevant factors on which to act to improve the quality of life. Discussion
 - c) Description of social relations in the rural environment
 - d) How collective initiatives can improve the quality of life in rural areas. Discussion.
- 4) Interventions related to the social dimension in rural areas of Aragon: what are the drivers and barriers in their implementation.

Eight MAP members attended the workshop representing research (3), society (4) and policy (1). The workshop was conducted by 2 members of the UPM team. No information was anticipated before the meeting.

The workshop was successfully carried out. Participants much appreciated to see the results of the surveys and the categorisation of the Aragonese counties according to their level of rurality. So far, there is no take-up of the results by MAP members.

Analysed the results of the preliminary workshop focused on the identification of the needs and the existing interventions to address them, a second workshop was held on the 3rd of October in Zaragoza (Aragón), focused on the definition of policy recommendations and the research opportunities to foster social relationships and social inclusion in rural areas. The workshop lasted four hours and it was structured as follows:

- Introduction: Presentation of the needs in the social field in the rural world in Aragon (identified in the previous workshop).
- Presentation of policies and initiatives implemented to cover the identified needs and actors involved.
- Definition of policy proposals to improve meeting the identified needs. Identify concrete actions and responsible actors. Discussion.
- Definition of research proposals to support overcoming the identified needs. Discussion.

Ten MAP members attended the workshop representing research (3), society (5) and policy (2). The workshop was conducted by three members of the UPM team. No information was anticipated before the meeting.

The workshop was successfully carried out. MAP members highlighted the opportunity brought for this kind of meetings to create the space to discuss about rural areas. So far, there is no take-up of the results by MAP members.

Annex 2 The survey

Presentation

The European Project SHERPA (<https://rural-interferences>) which involves 17 European Universities and Institutions aims to gather knowledge and opinions in order to formulate recommendations for future policies regarding EU's rural areas. Multi-Actor Platforms (MAP) have been set up for this purpose to exchange ideas for common learning and for co-creation of knowledge with different actors at European and regional level. So far, we have been working on the long-term vision for rural areas, the possibility of diversification of activities, and entrepreneurship. The results can be found on the project website.

We are now working on the social dimension of rural areas, including aspects related to the quality of life, social relationships and networks. To have a better understanding of these issues, we have prepared this short survey. We would be very grateful if you could answer it.

It will take you no more than 10 minutes to complete.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Personal Information

1.- Gender

Women

Men

2.- Indicate your occupation/profession

Agriculture

Livestock

Services

Public sector

Retiree

Other

3.- Where do you live?

Municipality

County

4.- Age

Survey

1.- Rate from 1 to 10 your quality of life.

2.- Rate from 1 to 7 how important you think the following aspects are to the quality of life in the place where you live.

Social relations (1=not important; 7=very important)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Living with the family	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Living close to friends and relatives	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Establishing social relations with the neighbours of the locality where you live	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Establishing social relations with the neighbours of the county where you live	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Participating in group activities	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Absence of major economic and cultural inequalities between neighbours	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of tension between groups (elderly, young people, migrants, new inhabitants).	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Living conditions (1=not important; 7=very important)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Security	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Natural environment	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Absence of overcrowding	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Absence of pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Absence of noise pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Low traffic	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Peace and quiet	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Access to employment and services (1=not important; 7=very important)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Existence of job opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Health services	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Education centres	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Housing	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Entertainment, Culture and Sports	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Banking services	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Shops and services (plumbing, consultancy services...)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Access to Internet	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Transport services	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Care centre for elderly	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Nurseries and childcare	<input type="checkbox"/>						

3.- Select the 8 aspects that most need to be improved to enhance the quality of life in the place where you live.

- Living with the family
- Living close to friends and relatives
- Establishing social relations with the neighbours of the locality where you live
- Establishing social relations with the neighbours of the county where you live
- Participating in group activities
- Absence of major economic and cultural inequalities between neighbours
- Lack of tension between groups (elderly, young people, migrants, new inhabitants).
- Security
- Natural environment
- Absence of overcrowding
- Absence of pollution
- Absence of noise pollution
- Low traffic
- Peace and quiet
- Existence of job opportunities
- Health services
- Education centres
- Housing
- Entertainment, Culture and Sports
- Banking services
- Shops and services (plumbing, consultancy services...)
- Access to Internet
- Transport services
- Care centre for elderly
- Nurseries and childcare

4.- Rate from 1 (not very limiting) to 7 (very limiting) the aspects that can condition the establishment of social relations in the place where you live.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Lack of time	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Absence or excessive distance to access a meeting place	<input type="checkbox"/>						
small number of people living in the locality	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of interest in social relations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Conflicting interests	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of trust in the results of collective action	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Cultural differences	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Negative relations from the past	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Local population closed to new ideas	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Age differences in the local population	<input type="checkbox"/>						

5.- Select the 3 meeting places where you think it is easiest to establish social relations in the place where you live

- Neighbouring centre / social place
- Educative centre
- Cultural centre
- Sport centre
- Bar / restaurant / nightlife place
- Shops
- Open public space
- Other

6.- In what aspects do you think it is easier to collaborate with the rest of the neighbours in your locality? (1=very easy; 7=very hard)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Entertainment/leisure activities	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Activities linked to educative centres	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Cultural activities	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Provision of mutual aid/assistance in work activities	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Neighbours' associations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Gastronomic meetings for the people of the village	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Organising events (music, gastronomic...) to attract visitors	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Organising new forms of service provision (transport, supply...)	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Activities intended for homogenous groups (young people, women, elderly...)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Value enhancement of local traditions	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Local heritage conservation	<input type="checkbox"/>						

7.- How would you define the social relations in the place where you live?

- Social relations are virtually non-existent
- Social relations are casual and superficial
- Social relations are daily and mutually supportive
- There are daily relations and joint projects are undertaken
- Some collectives are organised but do not involve the rest of the population
- Some collectives are organised and involve a big part of the population

8.- What is the level of participation of the following groups in the social life of the place where you live? (1=little participation; 7=a lot of participation)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Young people	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Adults	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Women	<input type="checkbox"/>						
National new settlers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Foreign new settlers	<input type="checkbox"/>						

9.- Are there concrete initiatives to encourage personal relations between neighbours and their participation in common actions?

- Yes
- No

If yes, briefly explain what they are and who is/are leading them.

10.- Would you like to add any relevant comments regarding the quality of life in rural areas?

Annex 3: Aspects explaining social relationships in rural areas

Note: From 1 (not very limiting) to 7 (very limiting)

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Annex 4: Places to establish social relationships in rural areas

Note: Number of times that the corresponding option has been selected by respondents

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Annex 5: Existing collaborative activities in rural areas

Note: 1= The collaborative activity is very easy to be established and 7= The collaborative activity is very complicated to be established.

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Annex 6: Characterisation of social relationships in rural areas

Note: Number of times that the corresponding option has been selected by respondents

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Annex 7: Participation in networks by social group

Note: 1=Very low participation; 7=Very high participation.

Source: Own elaboration based on the survey

Annex 8: Local Action Groups in Aragón

- 1. **CEDESOR** (Centro para el Desarrollo del Sobrarbe y la Ribagorza)
- 2. **ADEFO** (Asociación para el Desarrollo y el Fomento de las Cinco Villas)
- 3. **CEDER SOMONTANO** (Centro de Desarrollo Integral del Somontano)
- 4. **ASOMO** (Asociación para el Desarrollo de las Tierras del Moncayo)
- 5. **CEDER MONEGROS** (Centro de desarrollo Monegros)
- 6. **ADRI CALATAYUD ARANDA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Integral de la Comarca de Calatayud y del Aranda)
- 7. **CEDEMAR** (Centro para el Desarrollo de la Comarca del Mar de Aragón)
- 8. **ADRI JILOCA GALLOCANTA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Integral de las tierra del Jiloca y Gallocanta)
- 9. **ADIBAMA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Integral del Bajo Martín y Andorra - Sierra de Arcos)
- 10. **OMEZYMA** (Bajo Aragón - Matarraña)
- 11. **ASIADER** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Integral de la Sierra de Albarracín)
- 12. **AGUJAMA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo de Gúdar, Javalambre y Maestrazgo)
- 13. **FEDIVALCA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Integral de Valdejalón y Campo de Cariñena)
- 14. **ADRAE** (Asociación para el Desarrollo de la Ribera Alta del Ebro)
- 15. **OFYCUMI** (Oficina de Fomento y Desarrollo de la Comarca Cuencas Mineras)
- 16. **ADESHO** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Comarcal de la Hoya de Huesca)
- 17. **ADECABEL** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Integral de la Comarca de Campo Belchite)
- 18. **CEDER ZONA ORIENTAL HUESCA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo de la Zona Oriental de Huesca)
- 19. **ADECUARA** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Integral de la Cuna de Aragón)
- 20. **ADRI TERUEL** (Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural e Integral de la Comarca de Teruel)

Source: <https://aragonrural.org/grupos-leader/>

Annex 9: LAG budget 2014-2020 per inhabitant

Source: Own elaboration based on the LAGs' 2014-2016 strategic plans (ADECUARA (2017); ADEFO (2017); ADIBAMA (2017); ADRAE (2017); ADRI-Jiloca (2017); ADRI-Teruel (2017); ASIADER (2017); ASOMO (2017); CEDEMAR (2017); CEDER-Monegros (2017); CEDER-Somontano (2017); CEDERZO (2017); CEDESOR (2017); FEDIVALCA (2017); OFYCUMI (2017); OMEZYMA (2017)).

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